

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Ettah B. Essien & Florence Ettah Essien

Diversifying the Nigerian Economy Beyond Oil and Gas: Benefits and Threats

¹Ettah B. Essien, ²Florence Ettah Essien

¹Department of Economics, University of Uyo, Uyo

²Department of Economics, Akwa Ibom State University

¹essien.ettah@yahoo.com

Abstract

For over fifty years now, Nigeria has depended on revenue from oil for its fiscal operations and transactions. Oil prices at the global market have not been stable, and the volumes of oil produced in Nigeria have been fluctuating, with a consequent decrease in government revenue. However, the contributions of the non-oil sector to GDP and government revenue have been increasing. This indicates that there is a dire need to diversify the Nigerian economy into the non-oil sector. Diversifying the economy of a country is a process that requires a developmental state and a reasonable level of technological capability. Nigeria's major export commodity is oil. However, Nigeria does not possess the technology for oil exploration and production; thus, its oil sector is largely managed by foreign multinational corporations. For effective diversification in the non-oil sector, Nigeria should treat the development of its technological capability as a national project by giving adequate attention to the prime movers of technological progress. Among the prime movers, Nigeria should increase the number of researchers engaged in research and development (R&D) to about 500 per million people. It should also increase expenditure on R&D from 0.13% to 5% of its GDP.

Introduction

Nigeria has largely been depending on revenue from oil for its fiscal operations and transactions for over fifty years now. The prominence of the oil sector in the Nigerian economy started in the 1970s due to OPEC's oil embargo on the US in reprisal for the Arab-Israeli conflict (Okoji, 2000). Then the price of oil rose suddenly, and Nigeria's earnings from oil escalated from N4.733 billion in 1975 to N10.9 billion in 1979, and to N15.26 billion in 1980 (Olukoshi, 1990). With the sharp and marked increase in oil revenues that accrued to Nigeria, earnings from oil started to account for more than 90% of foreign exchange earnings, and 85 % of total exports. This development tended to

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Ettah B. Essien & Florence Ettah Essien

have diverted or reduced the nation's attention from adequately developing other sectors of the economy in addition to the oil sector.

Oil prices at the global market have not been stable. Between 1980 and 1983, prices of oil at the world market slashed due to oil glut, with a consequent decrease in oil revenue from N15.26 billion in 1980 to N 8.56 billion in 1981, and to N7.81 billion and N7.23 billion in 1982 and 1983, respectively. The fall in oil prices continued to 1986 when oil revenue was N8.12 billion (CBN, 2014).

It is, however, important to note that a country with one major export commodity stands a chance of bearing more risks and is susceptible and vulnerable to a sudden price drop on the international market. This is typical of Nigeria. For instance, due to a decrease in global oil prices between 2012 and 2016, Nigeria's oil revenue slumped from N8,879.0 billion in 2011 to N8,026.95 billion in 2012. It further dropped to N6,809.23 billion in 2013 and to N6,793.72 billion in 2014. In the last quarter of 2015, the price of oil dropped by 18.8 percent, with a consequent drop in the value of merchandise trade by 38.8 percent in the same quarter (Essien, 2018); yet, crude oil is still the dominant product in Nigeria's export basket, accounting for about 77.24% of total exports in the fourth quarter of 2022, with a value share of about 89% in Nigeria's export value (NBS, 2023).

Volumes of oil and gas produced in Nigeria have been decreasing. In 2019, average oil production in Nigeria was 2.01 mbpd; it decreased to 1.78 mbpd in 2020 (a 12.92% decrease). It further decreased to 1.60 mbpd in 2021. In 2022, average oil production in Nigeria was 1.37 mbpd (a 16.79% decrease from 2021 production). In 2023, on quarterly assessment (average), oil production was 1.54 mbpd in the first quarter, 1.22 mbpd in the second quarter, and 1.27 mbpd in the third quarter (NBS, 2022; NBS, 2023). Natural gas production in Nigeria has also been decreasing in the last four years. The volume of natural gas produced in Nigeria in 2019 was about 51,870,361 bcf. In 2020, it dropped to 49,947,292 bcf. It further dropped to 48,572,312 bcf in 2021 and to 44,307,050 bcf in 2022 (SRWER, 2023).

The fall in volumes of oil over the past few years and the fact that the trend is continuing strongly indicate that there is a dire need to diversify the Nigerian economy beyond oil and gas. This paper thus seeks to suggest the needed foundation for diversification in the Nigerian economy. It will present the benefits associated with the diversification of the economy when the needed foundation is laid, and the threats that

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Ettah B. Essien & Florence Ettah Essien

may be encountered if diversification is built on a faulty foundation. The paper will offer a policy mix to mitigate the threats.

The paper is organised as follows: following the introduction is section 2, which gives an overview of some concepts, and presents the needed foundation for diversification. Section 3 presents the analytical framework adopted for this paper. Section 4 suggests the direction of economic diversification in Nigeria, based on unfolding trends in global economic activity, and presents the prime-movers for diversification of the economy, while section 5 presents some lessons drawn from the oil sector. Section 6 concludes the study by offering policy options for maximising the opportunities and benefits associated with economic diversification and mitigating the threats. It is expected that the discussion would shed more light on the need for, and the direction of economic diversification in Nigeria.

2. Overview of some Concepts

2.1 The Economy

The economy is the collection of all productive activities in a society (Akpakpan, 1999:3). It can be used in the context of a whole country or a section of it. Thus, in this context, for instance, we could talk of the Nigerian economy, or the Akwa Ibom economy (a section of Nigeria), the American economy, or the Texas economy (a section of America), the Ghanaian economy, or the Ashanti economy (a section of Ghana). The economy can also be used in the context of the world; thus, we can talk of the global or world economy. According to Akpakpan (1999:3), the economy is abstract. We cannot see it; we cannot touch it. It is complex. Its constituents include banks, factories, schools, transport companies, construction companies, fishing companies, mining companies, eateries, trading businesses, and so on. The economy can, therefore, be seen as the collection of all the enterprises and other organisations that bring about the goods and services that are consumed (Akpakpan, 1999).

2.1.2 Diversification: Clarification and Benefits

Diversification is the act of branching out into diverse lines of activity. It is the act of developing a wider range of products, skills, and interests in order to be more successful or to reduce risk in business (Essien, 2018). Diversification, as argued by Black (2003:126), is the spread of the activities of a firm or a country between (or among) different types of markets. There are

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Ettah B. Essien & Florence Ettah Essien

multiple objectives a country seeks to achieve in diversifying its economy. These include: (i) to broaden the productive base of its economy by developing another or other profitable sector(s) in addition to the existing one(s) so as to make the economy virile and invulnerable to sudden price drops on the international market. This, if achieved, will reduce the dominance a particular product has had in the contents of the country's export basket. (ii) to earn more foreign exchange from the diversified structure of its export basket and increase its gross income, and (iii) to use the increased income to meet the socio-economic needs of its citizenry so as to improve their standard of living. A diversified economy bears less risk on the global market as the markets for its products are unlikely to slump at the same time (Essien, 2018; Black, 2003).

In this study, diversification of an economy is conceptualised as the development of other profitable sectors in addition to the existing one(s) for the economy to be viable and to reduce risks at the world market. Economic diversification, as we know, is a process and largely depends on industrialization—"the process of increasing an economy's capability to process raw materials and to produce goods for consumption and/or further production given its skills and efficiency, that is, technological adequacy" (Essien, 2004). The foundation for these development processes is a developmental state (Chang, 1999).

2.2 A Developmental State: The Foundation for Diversification

The foundation for effective economic diversification is a developmental state. In this subsection, we draw largely on Essien (2018). A developmental state, according to Johnson (1982), as contained in Essien (2018), is "a state that is focused on economic development and takes necessary policy measures to achieve that objective." However, Johnson (1982) pointed out two possible ways by which a state can develop, namely, the regulatory approach and the developmental approach. The regulatory approach applies when a state governs its economy through regulatory agencies that are empowered to enforce a variety of standards of behaviour to protect the citizenry against market failure of various sorts, while the developmental approach involves the state itself driving industrialization, as in the case of states that were late to industrialise their economies. The United States, for instance, according to Johnson (1982), follows a regulatory orientation, while Japan follows a developmental orientation because of its lateness to industrialization.

Also, Pempel (1999) conceptualised a developmental state as a government with organisation and power to achieve its development goals. The government in question must be able to give consistent economic guidance and efficient organisation to the economy. It must

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Etta B. Essien & Florence Etta Essien

pursue its long-term economic policy with vigour and steadfastness. As argued by Castells (1992), a state is said to be developmental if it establishes, as its principles of legitimacy and sovereignty, its ability to strategize, promote, and sustain development. Mkamdawire (2001) defined a developmental state as 'one whose ideological underpinnings are developmental and one that seriously attempts to construct and deploy its administrative and political resources to the task of economic development'. Evans (1989) fully agreed that the state has an active and positive role to play in the industrialization process, and attributed the success (or failure) of a developmental state to the capacity of the state to establish, promote, and sustain a healthy relationship between the state and private enterprise. A development state, according to Chang (1999), is "one that pursues policies focused on coordinating investment plans, has a national development vision, engages in institutional building to promote growth and development, and plays a crucial role in resolving the conflicts that arise out of the development trajectory between winners and losers. Specifically, Chang (1999) argued that "economic development requires a state that can create and regulate the economic and political relationships that can support industrialization." This implies that the leader in a developmental state must be *au fait* with the economy and the polity, and generally, the state must be capable of providing a vision for society and creating new institutions required to achieve the vision (Chang, 2003a). Leftwich (2000), in an analysis of a developmental state, gave primacy to politics; that is, a developmental state is centrally predicated on political considerations. He argued that politics is the dominant variable that determines the concept of a developmental state as well as its success or failure. He also emphatically submitted that "development inescapably is political." In other words, "...the explanation for the different development capabilities and records of the third-world democracies turns crucially on the primary role of politics in shaping the character and capacity of the state.

According to Leftwich (2000), as contained in Meyns and Musamba (2010), there are six major factors responsible for the emergence and consolidation of a developmental state. The developmental state:

- i. is governed by a political elite that is development-oriented and demonstrates high levels of commitment and will in attaining economic growth and development. The state must possess sufficient capacity to influence, direct, and set the terms of operation for private capital. Ekpo (2008:5), on this note, considering the level of development of the Nigerian economy, argued that "...the economy can be public-led but private-sector-driven".

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Ettah B. Essien & Florence Ettah Essien

- ii. is managed by a powerful, professional, highly competent, insulated, and career-based bureaucracy.
- iii. is associated with social contexts in which the presence and role of civil society have been weak, negligible, and subordinate.
- iv. must exhibit high levels of capacity for effective economic management of both domestic and foreign private economic interests.
- v. exhibits a record of an uneasy mix of expression and poor human rights adherence (especially for undemocratic development states, and
- vi. The legitimacy of the political elite to govern is tightly linked to the state's ability to perform.

Leftwich (2000) observed that most of the regimes in developmental states were undemocratic; however, they tended to be developmental. The argument is that “the development performance of a particular country is not a function of the regime type; rather, it is decisively influenced by the character of the state and its associated politics.” As such, “developmental states cannot be constructed out of institutional kits devised in western capitals.” Therefore, “it seems unlikely that it is possible in the modern world for any society to make a speedy and successful transition from poverty to affluence without a state that in some respects corresponds to (the above) model of a developmental state.

3 Analytical Framework

There are various approaches to examining any social phenomenon. In this section, we adopt Essien (2018) and uphold a developmental state, functional institutions, industrialization, among other factors, as catalytic to economic diversification. Our framework is based on the Institutional Political Economy (IPE) approach – An alternative to Economic Neo-Liberalism, and we draw on the works of Ha-Joon Chang of Cambridge University, UK. The IPE approach serves two major purposes. First, it consolidates an alternative theory of state intervention in the economy and, second, it provides an alternative framework to the Neo-Liberal paradigm. The role of the state in the economic development of developing countries, according to IPE, and we fully agree, is unrivalled; it is not only to regulate the market but to actually construct and directly influence its operations (Chang, 2000b). The IPE expressly argues that “virtually all today's developed countries (including the champions of free trade and free

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Ettah B. Essien & Florence Ettah Essien

markets, that is, Britain and the United States) became rich on the basis of policies that are contrary to the neo-liberal orthodoxy espoused under the Washington Consensus. It was the state that coordinated investments, made economic decisions, financed industries, disciplined recipients of state-created rent, and provided development vision in today's more-developed countries (MDCs) when they were developing; and this role by the state becomes even more important in the case of LDCs (Chang, 2003b). The success stories of the Asian Tigers, on unbiased evaluation, would lend credence to alternative approaches to the ones prescribed by the Washington Consensus. Wade (2004), on this note, argued that the economies of the highly praised Asian Tigers were not market-oriented as advocated by the neo-classical economists; rather, the state championed the development of many new industries and supported them to grow and become internationally competitive. "In contrast, all developing countries that have placed great faith in the primacy and the total freedom of the market have attained unsatisfactory development outcomes" (Chang, 2000c). According to Dos Santos (1993), who had observed the 'placing of great faith on the (free) market' by the LDCs', the unsatisfactory outcomes can only be changed through "a qualitative change in less-developed countries' internal structures and external relations." This is because the persistence and exacerbation of the unsatisfactory outcome (underdevelopment) are largely due to the historical evolution of a highly uneven international capitalist system of rich country-poor country relationship (Todaro and Smith, 2003: 124). In the process of climbing the ladder of development, we agree with IPE that today's high-income countries never adopted the neo-liberal doctrines they are pressuring the LDCs to adopt; they fully protected their infant industries through trade restrictions. On this note, we consent to IPE's argument that "economic development requires a state that can create and regulate the economic and political relationships that can support (and sustain) industrialization" (Chang, 1999), for the market is not a 'free' and 'neutral' institution, but all markets are created. In other words, "markets are political constructs," and as such, it is not possible to depoliticize them; thus, they need a state—a developmental state—to regulate them if they are to serve the desired purpose of development.

4. Diversifying the Nigerian Economy: Direction and the Prime movers

4.1 Diversifying the Nigerian Economy: Which Direction?

Due to the prominence of oil in Nigeria, the Nigerian economy is casually divided into 'oil' and

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Ettah B. Essien & Florence Ettah Essien

'non-oil' sectors. The non-oil sector is an umbrella term that covers other sectors such as agriculture, education, finance, industry, and services. Though oil is still dominant in Nigeria's export basket, accounting for about 68 percent of the total value of domestic exports, the non-oil sector has been contributing substantially to Nigeria's revenue and GDP, and the trend is continuing. For instance, in 2003, non-oil revenue was N500.82 billion. It increased to N1,336.0 billion in 2006. In 2010, it was N1,907.60 billion. In 2012 and 2013, non-oil revenue increased to N2,628.77 and N2,950.56 billion, respectively. In 2014, non-oil revenue in Nigeria reached N3,275.12 billion (CBN. 2014; Essien, 2018:125). A comparison of the contributions of the oil and non-oil sectors to Nigeria's GDP in the last seven years will show us the direction in our quest to diversify the Nigerian economy. Table 4.1 shows the quarterly and average contributions of the oil and non-oil sectors to Nigeria's GDP between 2017 and 2022. From Table 4.1, the average contribution of oil to GDP was 8.69%, while non-oil contributed 90.31% in 2017. In 2018, the share of oil in GDP decreased to 8.65%, while the share of non-oil in GDP increased to 91.35%. Oil's contribution to GDP was 8.82 in 2019, while non-oil contributed 91.18%.

Table 4.1: Quarterly and Average Contributions of Oil and Non-Oil Sectors to Nigeria's GDP, 2017 - 2022

OIL			NON-OIL		
Year	Quarterly contribution (%)		Year	Quarterly Contribution (%)	
2017	Q1	8.53	2017	Q1	91.47
	Q2	9.04		Q2	90.96
	Q3	9.84		Q3	90.16
	Q4	7.35		Q4	92.65
	Average	8.69		Average	90.31
2018	Q1	9.61	2018	Q1	90.39
	Q2	8.55		Q2	91.45
	Q3	9.38		Q3	90.62
	Q4	7.06		Q4	92.94
	Average	8.65		Average	91.35
2019	Q1	9.22	2019	Q1	90.78
	Q2	8.98		Q2	91.02
	Q3	9.77		Q3	90.23
	Q4	7.32		Q4	92.58
	Average	8.88		Average	91.95

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Etta B. Essien & Florence Etta Essien

2020	Q1	9.50	2020	Q1	90.50
	Q2	8.53		Q2	91.07
	Q3	8.72		Q3	90.27
	Q4	5.87		Q4	94.13
	Average	8.50		Average	91.50
2021	Q1	9.25	2021	Q1	90.75
	Q2	7.42		Q2	92.58
	Q3	7.49		Q3	92.51
	Q4	7.19		Q4	94.81
	Average	7.34		Average	92.66
2022	Q1	6.63	2022	Q1	93.37
	Q2	6.33		Q2	93.67
	Q3	5.66		Q3	94.34
	Q4	4.34		Q4	95.66
	Average	5.72		Average	94.26

**Sources: 1. National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), GDP Report, Q4 2020
2. National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), GDP Report, Q4 2022**

In 2022, the contribution of oil to GDP was 5.72% from 7.34% in 2021. On the contrary, the contribution of non-oil, which was 92.66% in 2021, increased to 94.26% in 2022. In the first quarter of 2023, oil contributed 6.21 percent to GDP, while non-oil contributed 93.79 percent. In 2023, the Federal Government projected that about N2.29 trillion of its revenue would come from oil, while N2.43 trillion would come from non-oil (NEPC, 2022).

The contributions of the non-oil sector to both government revenue and GDP, and the revenue the government expects the sector to yield in 2023, may serve as an indicator that the Nigerian economy has started diversifying into the non-oil sector. As we have stated earlier, diversifying an economy is a process, so more industrial development would be expected in the non-oil sector for sustained growth.

Also, following the unfolding global economic interest in what is termed the “Blue Economy,” we would suggest that the government should consider developing the country’s blue economy at an international level. The reason is that, currently, at

international forums, the concept of the blue economy is one major issue in global economic development discourse. The European Union sees the “blue economy” as “all economic activities related to oceans, seas, and coasts” (Udofia, 2023). The World Bank, as cited in Udofia (2023), describes the “blue economy” as “the sustainable use of ocean resources for economic growth, improved livelihoods, (and) jobs while preserving the health of the ocean ecosystem.” Udofia (2023) explains the “blue economy” in a more comprehensive way and refers to it as the “sustainable exploration and management of resources from the blue surfaces, whether off-shore, such as oceans, (or) on-shore such as seas, rivers, lakes, lagoons, ..., including artificial blue surfaces like dams and ponds.” The resources, as argued by Udofia (2023), have two major components: 1) the off-shore blue resources, that is, resources of the inland waters, such as dams, lakes, lagoons, and even wetlands and streams, all of which occur naturally; and 2) resources from artificial blue surfaces such as dams and ponds. The “blue economy,” as argued by Ekpo (2023), “oscillates around the marine sector; it focuses on vitalizing economic performance through marine activities such as mineral resource development, shipbuilding, communication cable laying, sustainable energy, fisheries and aquaculture, seaside leisure, construction, as well as pharmaceutical enterprises, among others.” The blue economy aims to fully utilise and explore the ocean and its associated activities (Ekpo, 2023). Opportunities associated with the blue economy are enormous, and about 70% of the earth’s resources are underneath the sea and, in most cases, left untapped. For a country to fully tap the untapped resources of the blue economy, it needs to have acquired a substantial level of technology, as technological capability constitutes the prime movers of industrialization.

4.2 Diversifying the Economy: The Prime Movers

Diversifying the economy of a country is a process that needs adequate preparation. It is part of the nation's industrialization pursuit. Therefore, the country needs a reasonable level of technological capability upon which its industrialization rests. Industrialization is a process of building up a society's (or a country's) capacity to harness and process raw materials to produce goods and services for consumption, and further production or export. This process is roundly a function of the level and quality of technological capability of the society (or country). Technological capability is the capacity and competence to innovate and invent scientific knowledge, processes, products, methods,

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Ettah B. Essien & Florence Ettah Essien

and systems, and to apply them in the management of the projects concerned. It involves the knowledge and skills to design, fabricate the necessary machines and tools, and to install and operate the productive system for production of goods (Essien, 2004; Essien, 2017: 30).

In the light of technological capability and industrialization, we will assess Nigeria's stance in a pool of countries. This will help us to assess Nigeria's level of preparedness for profitable diversification to the non-oil sector and the blue economy. We will adopt four major indices of technological capability used by UNESCO INSTITUTE OF STATISTIC (UJS) (2022). These indices are: (1) Innovation index (1 - 100), (2) Number of researchers per million people in research and Development (R&D), (3) Expenditure on R&D as percentage of GDP, and (4) Value of high technology exports (expressed in \$ million). Table 4.2 shows the innovation index of selected countries in a pool of 128 countries.

Table 4.2: Innovation Index of Selected Countries, 2022

Country	Innovation (0 – 100)	Global Index
Switzerland	64.6	1
USA	61.8	2
Sweden	61.6	3
UK	59.7	4
Netherlands	58	5
South Korea	57.8	6
Singapore	57.3	7
Germany	57.2	8
Finland	56.9	9
Denmark	55.9	10
Nigeria	16.9	113

Source: World Intellectual Property Organization, 2022

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Etta B. Essien & Florence Etta Essien

Note: *Innovation is the application of inventions of new production processes and methods to production activities, as well as the introduction of new products. Innovations may include the introduction of new social and institutional methods of organisation and management commensurate with modern ways of conducting economic activities (Todaro and Smith, 2011).*

Global Innovation Index is the ranking of countries by their capacity for and success in innovation

Table 4.2 shows countries' capacity and success in innovation in 2022. Switzerland with 64.6 was ranked first, followed by USA with 61.8. UK scored 59.7 and was ranked fourth. Denmark was ranked tenth with a score of 55.9. Nigeria, in a pool of 128 countries was ranked 113 with a score of 16.9. Nigeria's position in innovation is very poor. Three of the top ten countries in innovation in 2022 were also among the best four countries in technological capability ranking (0 – 10) in 2023. South Korea with a score of 6.63 was ranked first, followed by USA with a score of 4.94. Taiwan was ranked third with a score of 4.90, while Denmark scored 4.79, and was ranked fourth.

Another index of technological capability is number of researchers in research and development (R&D) (per million people). Researchers in R&D are professionals engaged in the conception and creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods, or systems. They are also engaged in the management the projects concerned. It includes doctor of philosophy (PhD) students engaged in R&D. Table 4.3 shows number of researchers in R&D (per million people) in selected countries between 2015 and 2020.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Ettah B. Essien & Florence Ettah Essien

Table 4.3: Researchers in R&D (per million people) in selected countries, 2015 – 2020

COUNTRY	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Russia	3098	2952	2822	3784	2747	2722
France	4307	4415	4570	4700	4812	4926
USA	4258	4251	4412	4749	4821	Na
UK	4320	4358	4435	4554	4638	Na
Germany	4744	4862	5077	5217	5396	5393
Tunisia	1799	1997	1946	1812	1745	1660
Singapore	7007	6935	6815	6825	7287	na
China	1089	1151	1197	1307	1471	1585
South Korea	7013	7086	7498	7980	8408	8714
Japan	5173	5209	5304	5331	5377	5455
Nigeria	39	na	na	na	na	na

World Bank, World Development Indicators, 2022

NOTE: Researchers in R&D are professionals engaged in conceiving of or creating new knowledge, products, processes, methods, and systems and in managing the projects concerned. (World Development Indicators, 2022).

The role of researchers in R&D is unrivalled. Researchers in R&D are indispensable in technological development. Russia engaged 3,098 researchers (per million people) in R&D in 2015, and increased to 3784 in 2018. In 2020, Russia engaged 2722 researchers (per million people) in R&D. France engaged 4307 researchers (per million) people in 2015, and increased the number to 4926 in 2020. South Korea engaged 7013 researchers (per million people) in R&D 2015 and increased the number to 8714 in 2020. Between 2015 and 2020, Japan increased the number of its researcher in R&D (per million people) from 5173 to 5455. Nigeria, on the contrary, engaged only 39 researchers in R&D in 2015. This is not encouraging in a developing economy like Nigeria.

Another essential prime mover of technological development is the percentage of GDP expended on R&D. Table 4.4 shows expenditures on R&D (as percentage of GDP) in selected countries.

**Table 4.4: Expenditures for R&D* (as Percentage of GDP) in Selected Countries, 2022 **

\ Country	Expenditure on R&D (% of GDP)
Germany	3.14
Denmark	2.96
France	2.34
Japan	3.26
South Korea	4.81
USA	3.46
Sweden	3.53
China	2.4
Switzerland	3.15
Nigeria	0.13
Togo	0.27

World Bank, World Development Report, 2022

* *Expenditure for R&D are current and capital expenditures on creative work undertaken to increase the stock of knowledge in the society and the use of knowledge to devise new application (World Development Report, 2022).*

From Table 4.4, Nigeria's expenditure on R&D in 2022 was the least, with 0.13 % of its GDP. South Korea expended 4.81 % of its GDP on R&D in 2022. Sweden, USA, Japan and Germany and Switzerland, already more – developed countries, expended more than 3% of their GDPs on R&D. The very low expenditure on R&D, among other factors, suggests why the level and quality of technology in Nigeria is yet low.

Another indicator of technological capability of countries is the value of their high-tech export products at the international market. Table 4.5 mirrors the values of high-tech export products of selected countries in a pool of 98 countries in 2021. High – tech export products are products with high R&D intensity such as computers, pharmaceuticals, scientific instruments, electrical machinery, etc. (World Development Indicators, 2022).

Table 4.5: Values of High – tech Export Products of Selected Countries, 2021

Country	Value of High -tech exports (\$ M)	Global Rank
China	942314.82	1
Hong Kong	431628.78	2
Germany	209744.31	3
USA	169217.26	4
Japan	116513.86	5
Malaysia	108683.18	6
Netherlands	101168.44	7
France	97528.03	8
Mexico	74932.49	9
UK	66699.92	10
Egypt	526.18	51
Nigeria	195.95	60
Benin	1.12	89

Source: World Bank, 2022

The finesse of a product is defined by the quality of technology congealed in the product. This then determines the value of the product. High- tech products depend largely on innovation, number of researchers in R&D, number of technicians in R&D, and the percentage of GDP expended on R&D. The value of high-tech products from China at the international market in 2021 was \$942,314.82 million. This placed China in the first position among the ten countries with high-tech exports in 2021. Germany was ranked 3rd, Japan 5th, France 8th and UK 10th. Nigeria's high-tech products at the international market in 2021 valued \$195.95 million, which placed Nigeria in the 60th position in a pool of 98 countries. It is important to know that the top ten countries in high-tech products at the international market place importance on technological capability by engaging substantial number of researchers in R&D and funding R&D adequately.

A country with high technological capability will have a strong manufacturing

sector, which is the nucleus of a virile industrial sector. Table 4.6 shows top ten manufacturing countries in the world, their percentage contributions to global manufacturing, values of their products and their main export products.

Table 4.6 Top Ten Manufacturing Countries in the World

Country/ Global ranking	% contribution to Global Manufacturing	Monetary contribution to Global Economy (\$)	Main Export Products
1. China	28	4 trillion	Textiles, garments, electronics
2. USA	18	1.8 trillion	Automobile, food, chemicals, aircraft, military equipment
3. Japan	10	700 billion	Vehicles, computers, chemicals
4. Germany	7	Na	Motor vehicles, electrical machinery
5. South Korea	4	372 billion	Electronic products, transportation equipment
6. India	3	298 billion	Agricultural products, engineering goods, textiles, leather products, chemicals
7. France	3	274 billion	Agricultural products, transport equipment, machines, wines
8. Italy	3	256 billion	Clothing, wines, chemicals, transport equipment, machinery
9. UK	2	244billion	Chemicals, food
10. Mexico	2	175 billion	Lubricants, food, transport equipment, machinery

Source: SRWER, 2023

From Table 4.6, China, in 2022 contributed 28 % to global manufacturing, and contributed \$4 trillion to global economy. It was ranked 1st as a country with the best manufacturing sector. The USA was ranked 2nd with \$1.8 trillion contribution to global economy. France contributed 3% to global manufacturing, while UK and Mexico

contributed 2% each. The top 10 manufacturing countries pay attention to R&D. For instance, south Korea, in 2022, expended 4.81 % of its GDP on R&D, and engaged 8714 researchers per million people in R&D. Germany expended 3.14% of its GDP on R&D and engaged 5393 researchers per million people in R&D in 2022. France expended 3.34 % of its GDP on R&D, and engaged 4926 researchers in R&D in 2022, while UK engaged 4821 researchers per million people in R&D, and expended 3.4% of its GDP on R&D in 2019. As we have seen in Table 4.4, Nigeria expended 0.13 % of its GDP on R&D and engaged 39 researchers per million people in 2015 (see Tables 4.3 and 4.4).

5. Diversifying the Nigerian Economy: Lessons from the Oil Sector

The non-oil sector in Nigeria is gaining prominence due to its increasing contributions to GDP and Government revenue. This suggests that the Nigerian economy is diversifying from oil to non-oil sector. The unfolding global economic interest in the Blue Economy also suggests that Nigeria should develop its blue economy to international level. The question is: does Nigeria have the technological capability to develop its non-oil sector and its blue economy with minimal dependence on the West? Gleaning from the Nigerian oil sector, major operators in the sector are companies from the MDCs. The reason for this is simple: who possesses the technological capability in a particular sector controls and manages production in that sector. Table 4.7 shows some major petroleum and exploratory companies in Nigeria and their mother countries.

Tabl4 4.7: Some Major Petroleum and Exploratory Companies in Nigeria and their Mother Countries

	Some Petroleum and Exploratory Companies in Nigeria	Mother Country
1	Shell	UK
2	Chevron	USA
3	Statoil	Norway
4	Exxon Mobil	USA
5	Nigerian Agip Exploration (NAE)	Italy
6	Addax Petroleum Exploration (Nig.)	China
7	Total Upstream Nigeria	USA
8	Conoco Energy Nigeria	USA
9	ELF Petroleum Nigeria (EPNL)	France
10	Addax Petroleum Development	China

Source: SRWER, 2023

From Table 4.7, the oil sector in Nigeria is largely controlled and managed by the MDCs. Why?

The glaring answer is that they have the technology needed in the sector.

5.1 The Threats

Nigeria's technological capability is weak. Its innovation index is low. The value of Nigeria's high-tech exports is relatively very low. Without adequate and conscious development of technological capability in Nigeria, diversifying to the non-oil sector will not be of great benefit to Nigeria. The same countries that control Nigeria's oil sector through their multinational companies, will also use their technology to control Nigeria's non-oil sector and its blue economy. Thus, the pace of industrialization and development in Nigeria largely will be controlled by the multinational companies; for technology is the driver of industrialization and development.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusion

If Nigeria, indeed, wants to diversify to its non-oil sector, and to develop its blue economy, it is essential that Nigeria takes the development of its technological capability as a national question by giving adequate attention to the prime movers of technological progress – number of researchers and technicians in R&D, expenditure on R&D; steady public power supply, etc. Countries are qualified as either more-developed or less-developed based on the level and quality of technology they possess.

6.2 Recommendations

To mitigate the threats, Nigeria should consciously:

- a) engage more researchers in R&D. This can be done by engaging Bachelor of Science, Master of science and Doctor of Philosophy students whose projects, dissertations and theses are on R&D. Students in technical schools who also involve in R&D projects should be engaged in national R&D.
- b) increase the percentage of its GDP for R&D to 5.0 percent. This will help to increase the provision for more researchers and technicians to be employed in R&D.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Etta B. Essien & Florence Etta Essien

References

- Akpakpan, E. B. (1999). *The Economy: Towards a New Type of Economics*, Delpot Publishers, Port Harcourt.
- Black, J. (2003), *Dictionary of Economics*, Oxford University Press, Oxford
- Castells, M. (1992), *Four Asian Tigers with a Dragon Head: A Comparative Analysis of the State, Economy and Society in the Asian Rim*, in Applebaum, R. P. and Henderson, J. (eds.): *State and Development in the Asian Pacific Rim*, Sage, London, 176–198.
- Central Bank of Nigeria, CBN, (2014), *Statistical Bulletin*, Vol. 25. December, pp. 145 - 147
- Chang, H. (1999), *The Economic Theory of the Developmental State*, in Woo-Cumings (ed), *The Developmental State*, Cornell University Press, Ithaca, 182-199.
- Chang, H.(2000b). *An Institutional Perspective on the Role of the State: Towards an Institutional Political Economy*, in Burlamaqui, L et al (eds). *Institutions and the Role of the State*, Edward Elgar, Aldershot, 3-26.
- Chang, H. (2003a), *Globalization, Economic Development and the Role of the State*, Zed Books, London.
- Dos Santos, T. (2003), *The Structure of Dependence*, in Seligson, M. A. and Passéé – Smith, J. T.(eds.) *Development and Underdevelopment: The Political Economy of Inequality*, Lynne Rienner Publishers, London, 193 – 202.
- Ekpo, A. H. (2023), “Blue Economy: Opportunities and Challenges for the Private Sector”, A paper presented at the COSSCCIMA Maiden Blue Economy Summit at Watbridge Hotel and Suits, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, May 11.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Etta B. Essien & Florence Etta Essien

- Ekpo, A. H. (2008). 'The Nigerian Economy: Is it at the Crossroads?', Presidential Address Delivered at the 49 th Annual Conference of the Nigerian Economic Society, at Sharaton Hotel and Towers, Abuja, Nigeria, August 26.
- Essien, E. B. (2004). Developing and Sustaining Indigenous Technology for Sustainable Industrialization in Nigeria” in: *Challenges of Nigerian Industrialization: A Pathway to Nigeria Becoming a Highly Industrialized Country in the Year 2015*. Nigerian Economic Society (NES), Ibadan: Multi Media Publishers Ltd., 463-490.
- Essien, E. B. (2017). Technological Capability and Industrialization in Nigeria: A Political Economy Perspective, in *Gusau International Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 27 – 48.
- Essien, E. B. (2018). Political Economy Considerations in Diversification of the Nigerian Economy, in *South South Journal of Culture and Development*, Vol. 20, No. 1, pp. 122 – 169.
- Evans, P. B. (1989), Predatory, Developmental and other State-Apparatuses: A Comparative Political Economy Perspective on the Third World State, in *Sociological Forum*, 4(4): 561–587.
- Johnson, C. (1982). MITI and the Japanese Miracle: The Growth of Industrial Policy, 1925 – 1975. Stanford University Press, Stanford.
- Leftwich, A. (2000). *State of Development: On the Primacy of Politics in Development*, Polity Press, Cambridge.
- Mkandawire, T. (2001). Thinking about Developmental State in Africa, in *Cambridge Journal of Economics*, 25(3): 289 -213
- Meynes, P. and Musamba, C. ((2010), *The Developmental State in Africa: Problems and Prospect*, Institute for Entwicklung and Frieden (INEF) Report, 101/2010.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Etta B. Essien & Florence Etta Essien

National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Gross Domestic Product Report, Q 4, 2020.

National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Gross Domestic Product Report, Q 4, 2022

National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Gross Domestic Product Report, Q 1, 2023.

Okoji, M. A. (2000), "Petroleum Oil and the Niger-Delta Environment", *International Journal of Environmental Studies*, OPA, N.V., Malaysia, 57:713 – 723.

Olukoshi, A.O. (1990) 'The Role of the International Monetary Fund and World Bank in the Management of Nigeria's Foreign Debt', in Olukosi, A. O. (ed.) *Nigeria's Eternal Debt Crisis: Its Management*, NIIA and Malthouse, Lagos, 84.

Pempel, T. J. (1999), The Developmental Regime in a Changing World Economy, in Woo-Cumings (ed.), *The Developmental State*, Cornell University Press, Ithaca, 137 – 181.

Statistical Review of World Energy Report, June 2023.

Thompson, M. (1996), Late Industrialisers, Late Democratizers: Developmental State in Asia-Pacific, *Third World Quarterly*, Vol. 17, No.4, 625 – 647.

Todaro, M. P. and Smith, S. C. (2003). *Economic Development*, 8th Edition, Pearson Education Pte Ltd., Delhi.

Udofia, E. P. (2023), 'Harnessing Blue Resources for the Development of Akwa Ibom State', A Keynote Paper Presented at the Round Table Discussion on the Blue Economy, Organized by the Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Uyo, Uyo, Nigeria.

UNESCO Institute of Statistics (UIS), 2022.

Wade, R. (2004), *Governing the Market: Theory and the Role of Government in East Asia*, Princeton University Press, Princeton.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Ettah B. Essien & Florence Ettah Essien

World Bank, *World Development Indicators*, 2011

World Bank, *World Development Indicators*, 2022

World Development Reports, 2022

World Intellectual Property Organization, 2022

Woo-Cumings, M. (1999), *The Developmental State*. Cornell University Press, Ithaca